

“As light as a leaf”: Product Metaphor Generation for Experience-Driven Design

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Abstract: Metaphors are effective tools for experience-driven design since they are a powerful means for expressing the meaning of products. To generate a metaphor, designers have to select a ‘source’ conveying a meaning, take at least one attribute from this source and transfer it to the product they design (i.e. target product). In this paper, the reason why particular entities are selected as ‘source’ and how certain attributes of that source are mapped onto the target product are addressed. A workshop was conducted with design students who were instructed to convey ‘lightness’ in their designs by way of a metaphor. The workshop outcomes indicate that when looking for source domains, students got inspiration from concrete entities from nature, biology, everyday objects, actions or other cultural artifacts. They select entities from these domains as sources if they convey their intended meaning saliently and match appropriately with the attributes of the target product. After selecting the source, its sensorial properties, movements and/or interaction patterns are mapped onto the attributes of the target product. This workshop is one of the first attempts to include metaphors as a research subject in product design, and aims to contribute to product experience knowledge by providing a source for creating meaningful and pleasurable experiences.

Keywords: *Product metaphors, Metaphor generation, Source selection, Metaphors in design.*

1. Introduction

Rather than being merely utilitarian tools, products are means for pleasurable and meaningful experiences. For this reason, designers have the responsibility of “not only designing products that work well, but also of designing products that provide people with pleasurable experiences or the needed support in their quest for a meaningful life.” [13] Metaphors are very effective in achieving these goals of experience-driven design. They can make abstract ideas concrete and thus turn a complex product into a comprehensible one or they can be used to promote pleasurable user-product interactions by emphasizing the function, social or cultural meaning, or personality of a product. Therefore, they have a direct and substantial influence on the meanings and values we attach to products and the use of them leads to rich sensorial and emotional experiences.

Metaphors involve an association between conceptually separate entities where the attributes related to one conceptual entity are used to understand or represent some other conceptual entity [14]. They are frequently used in everyday language and literature (i.e. verbal metaphors), and there is a huge body of research from linguistics, philosophy and psychology disciplines investigating them extensively. However, they are also valuable tools for communication in product design where they are used for expressing and enhancing the meaning of products. Designers create metaphors by taking attribute(s) from one entity and transferring it to the product they design. For instance, in the product metaphor seen in Figure 1, the designer implies an association between a coffee machine and a butler. By using this metaphor, he/she reminds us of the main function of coffee makers, i.e. serving coffee, by giving an implicit reference to the serving posture of butlers. Consequently, he/she successfully conveys the meaning of courtesy, and provides a novel and pleasurable interaction with the product.

Figure 1. Senseo coffee maker from Philips

In technical terms (adapted from literary theory), the coffee-machine is referred to as the ‘target’ of the metaphor, which is the product that is designed to convey meaning. Butler is referred to as the ‘source’, indicating the entity imported to alter the target for communicating that particular meaning. Actually, both target and source are part of extensive networks of facts, connoted meanings, metonymic extensions, attitudes, emotions, etc. [3]. That’s why it is common to refer to target and source as target and source ‘domains’. In every metaphor there is at least one attribute from the source domain that is mapped onto a matching attribute in the target domain. In our example, these mapped attributes are the bended posture and the serving plate of the servant, and these are aptly reflected in the appearance of the coffee maker. However, it should be noted that making mapping between two separate entities is not enough to be entitled as a metaphor. The use of metaphor involves a transfer of ‘meaning’ from one domain to another; otherwise the construction is simply an analogy that just builds a similarity between two things [13].

With the intention of providing a coherent overview on product metaphor experience, Cila and Hekkert [1] proposed a framework systematically gathering the variety of factors found in linguistics literature and adapting them to products through analyzing various product metaphor samples. In this framework, metaphor is considered as a creative communication process between the designer and user. These parties create the metaphorical meaning together since the product metaphor mediates between the intentions of the designer to generate the metaphor, and the experience (i.e. reception, interaction, comprehension, evaluation and affective reaction) of the users. In this paper, we focus on the designer side of the framework and explore the metaphor

generation process of designers: Why do designers select certain entities as source domains for the metaphors they generate, and how do they map attributes of this source to the target product. Since so little is known in the literature about this topic, we conducted a workshop with design students and asked them to generate product metaphors to convey a particular meaning. The nature of the source domains they used in their designs and their mapping processes were analyzed in order to obtain an understanding of metaphor generation.

Before presenting the workshop design and results, we will first discuss some theoretical models from linguistics domain that deal with metaphor generation. We will later describe how our results can be interpreted in the light of these models. This study aims to be an initial step in linking the linguistic theories of metaphor to the domain of products, and contribute to design knowledge by providing a means for creating pleasurable product experiences.

2. Selecting source domains during metaphor generation

2.1. Verbal metaphors

Metaphor generation is described to involve two consecutive phases: (1) finding a source domain that can be used for generating a metaphor relevant to a target domain, (2) making the mapping from that source to the target domain [7]. Current research in the linguistics domain mainly deals with the second step of this process since the participants are usually given pre-identified source domains and are asked to select among them [8]. For instance, Katz [6] gave participants sentence-completion tasks and found out that people prefer to complete metaphor sentences with ‘concrete’ rather than more abstract sources. Clevenger Jr. and Edwards [2] revealed that selected sources are semantically closer to the target domain compared to unselected sources. Pierce and Chiappe [11] investigated the factors affecting source selection and found out that conventionality of the metaphor sentence influences the quality of sources and the time it takes to generate them.

Next to these studies, some others build models on the cognitive mechanisms behind this process. These models suggest that metaphors are produced and understood in a similar way, and they deal with metaphor production like it is the reverse process of comprehension [2, 11, 12, 14]. Therefore, they try to broaden existing models on metaphor comprehension to cover generation processes. One of these existing models is the ‘correspondence model’, which views metaphor as a kind of analogy and asserts that the perception of similarity is the basis of metaphor use and comprehension [9]. Let’s take the verbal metaphor example of ‘the body is a machine’. According to this view, ‘body’ and ‘machine’ have some shared attributes like having a complex mechanism, needing maintenance, using energy, etc. Therefore, people search for common relational features between body and machine in order to understand this metaphor. In terms of metaphor production, this view implies a two-stage process [11]. In the first stage, a list of attributes of the target is generated. By this way, potential sources sharing similar attributes are identified. Then, in the second stage, a source domain showing the greatest overlap with the target attributes is chosen [12]. However, the correspondence model is quite vague in terms of the criteria to which the attributes of the target are listed. Without any guidance, a speaker may provide a substantially expanding list of relevant attributes. However, there should be a concept/meaning that confines this list by providing a focus point. Furthermore, it is claimed by this model that the source having the most shared properties with the target is chosen. Yet, this approach may fit better to an analogy creating process rather than

metaphor generation. As mentioned in the introduction, metaphors involve a transfer of meaning provided by the association between two entities instead of mere correspondence among them. For these reasons, we believe that this model does not fully explain the metaphor generation process and it requires modifications and further detailing.

With similar concerns, Glucksberg and his colleagues [4-5] proposed a categorization-based approach as an alternative to correspondence models. Their ‘Interactive Property Attribution Model’ does not assume a comparison between target and source. According to the model, target and source are never placed in direct correspondence during metaphor comprehension, but people construct a superordinate category that the source typifies and consider the target as a member of this category. To illustrate this approach, in the previous example ‘machine’ typifies the category of things that ‘have a complex mechanism’. Because the target ‘body’ is understood as a member of this category, it automatically inherits the relevant features of that category. On the other hand, ‘machine’ may also address the category of things that are ‘noisy’ or even ‘soulless’. However, the target domain indicates which dimension is relevant in the metaphoric sentence. Therefore, in this model target and source domains perform different functions. Particularly, the source provides properties for attribution, whereas the target constrains which dimensions are relevant for attribution [4]. In terms of metaphor production, this theory implies that the choice of a source is determined by the properties being attributed to the target, rather than the target domain itself. This means that when people generate a metaphor, they have a meaning in mind that they want to attribute to the target and look for a source domain that is a good exemplar of that particular meaning [11]. Yet again, this selection does not depend on the target that is employed; instead, the target plays a role in providing the relevant dimensions for attribution. This is a source-driven approach in that the knowledge associated with the source influences our understanding of target [14].

We consider interactive property attribution model to better explain the metaphor generation process. Metaphors are means for communication, and consequently their main purpose is to express meaning effectively. Interactive property attribution model explicitly suggests that metaphor generation starts with a ‘meaning’ to convey, then source domains are chosen according to this meaning. Therefore, it is appropriate to add a preliminary step of ‘defining the meaning’ to the two-phased metaphor generation process that has been mentioned at the beginning of this section [7]. Summarizing, metaphor generation starts with defining the meaning which one intends to convey through the metaphor usage, proceeds with selecting a source domain representing that particular meaning, and ends with making a mapping from that source to the target domain in order to modify the target to convey the intended meaning (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Metaphor generation process

2.2. Product metaphors

In addition to the studies found in linguistics, there are a few studies related to generation of metaphors in the design domain as well. To start with, Müller [10] mentions two design cases where designers created product metaphors. Although he considers both cases as involving metaphor design processes, it would be convenient to

point out the differences between the two. The first example is a new form concept for a vacuum cleaner. In the idea creation process, the designer aimed to emphasize the strong suction power of the vacuum cleaner and make the function of the product recognizable. Thus, he associated the hose of the vacuum cleaner with the trunk of an elephant. Then, he explicitly transferred the form characteristics of the source domain (i.e. elephant) onto the appearance of the target (i.e. vacuum cleaner). In the second example, the author refers to a student project of pruning shears. The student coincidentally perceived the action of squeezing a hairbrush in the palm of his hand, where the brush bends and bristles appear. He associated this action with his project, and designed a pruning shear that fits at hand like a brush and the action of grabbing and holding were associated with pruning. The first case is an example of a metaphor generation process where the designer of the vacuum cleaner wanted to convey the message of power and effectiveness. With this intention, he thought of potential sources he could use in his design and came up with the ‘elephant’ source because of the animal’s strong suction power. This approach corresponds with the interactive property attribution model. On the other hand, the second case is more of an analogical reasoning process where the designer perceived the action of the hairbrush by chance, and associated it with the action of the pruning shear. This association improved the working mechanism of pruning shears but there is no meaning transfer that is provided by this association. This kind of process that involves seeing an immediate connection between two separate things and bringing them together is also important in design processes [10], however it cannot be entitled as metaphorical thinking in our view.

Similar to Müller, Madsen [8] also collected some design cases where metaphors had been consciously or unconsciously used, and proposed a set of guidelines for metaphorical design. These include building on already existing metaphors, using predecessor artifacts as metaphors, being aware of the metaphors already implicit in the problem definition, looking for real world events exhibiting key aspects, looking for new meanings for the concept, and creating a well-understood metaphor with a rich structure and suitable to the audience. Although these guidelines are quite general in terms of content, they give some insights about what designers aim when generating metaphors and where designers look for when selecting metaphors.

To summarize, we can state that research on metaphor generation is at early stage, even in the linguistics domain. Most studies are concentrated on how people understand or evaluate metaphors rather than on how they produce new metaphors. Therefore, we aim to make an initial attempt to understand this generation process by conducting a workshop.

3. Workshop on Metaphor Generation

3.1. Goal and Context

The goal of this workshop is to get an understanding on why certain entities are chosen as source domains while designers are generating metaphors and how designers make mapping from this selected source to the target product. This workshop was conducted within the scope of the Project Exploring Interactions course at Delft University of Technology, Master of Design for Interaction. 16 master students (8 male/8 female) who are taking this course volunteered to participate in the workshop. Each year there is a specific theme of the course that the students design for. When the workshop took place, the selected theme was ‘lightness’. This theme was also used in the workshop since students would benefit from the process during their own projects, and lightness is a

rich concept that can help finding different source domains for metaphors. We followed the approach of interactive property attribution model and asked the students to start metaphor generation with the aim of conveying meaning. Consequently, the students were given the meaning of 'lightness' to communicate through product metaphors. In order to do that, four different product types were chosen: MP3 player, package for potato chips, bus stop and automatic teller machine (ATM). When choosing these products, it was taken into consideration that they have diverse qualities in certain aspects as size (big-medium-small), interaction type (one-to-one, one-to-many), mode (digital-analogue), and ownership (consumer product-public product).

The workshop started with an introduction on the aim of the workshop, and the students were given a 20 minutes presentation on product metaphors in order to familiarize them with the technical terms. Then, each student was assigned randomly to one of four product types, and they were given the design brief of: "Design a that conveys the meaning of 'lightness' with the use of a metaphor". They were told to explore 'lightness' concept as extensively as possible in the first hour. After this exploration phase, they were instructed to proceed to the design phase by focusing on a source that would convey this meaning and make a mapping from that source onto the product they were assigned to. Next, they were asked to refine their ideas with a final presentation sketch. This phase took 1.5 hours. After the completion of the sketches, the group came together and each student presented his/her project. This stage was video recorded while the students explained how they chose to convey lightness, what was their source domain and why they chose it.

3.2. Results and Analysis

3.2.1. Defining the meaning

As aforementioned, the design process started with an exploration phase in which the students were encouraged to discover various dimensions of the lightness concept. In this stage, most of the students provided a very comprehensive presentation of lightness varying from related physical properties (e.g. transparent, odorless, lemon taste, emptiness) to associated actions (e.g. flying, jumping, floating) and concepts (e.g. simplicity, meditation, drugs, air) through mind maps or lists. It was observed that lightness was considered to be a vague concept, which the students felt the need to clarify. Therefore, they defined how they interpret lightness and what kind of lightness they would convey through their designs further in detail. When these lightness types are categorized, we see the students chose four different approaches:

- (1) Lightness in terms of being **light in weight** (10 out of 16 students)
- (2) Lightness in terms of being **effortless, fun** (4 out of 16 students)
- (3) Lightness in terms of being **diet, fat-free** (1 out of 16 students)
- (4) Lightness in terms of being **peaceful, stress-free** (1 out of 16 students)

As can be seen above, most of the students focused on the weight dimension of lightness. This was an expected approach since being light in weight is the denotative meaning of lightness. On the other hand, the remaining students focused on its connotative meanings and preferred to emphasize different aspects of lightness through their designs.

3.2.2. Finding a source domain to convey that particular meaning

After clarifying the lightness dimension they will focus on, students made explorative sketches with the potential source domains that are likely to express that particular dimension. Including both the initial sketches and final presentations, the total number of product metaphor ideas obtained in this stage was 57. 16 out of these 57 product metaphor concepts made their way to the final presentations. Table 1 summarizes the source domains considered in the exploration phase together with the ones selected for the final sketches; they are categorized according to the subject areas they belong to.

Table 1. The source domains used in initial and final sketches.

	Man-made objects		Nature related entities		Living things		Actions		Cultural phenomena	
	Initial sketches	Final sketches	Initial sketches	Final sketches	Initial sketches	Final sketches	Initial sketches	Final sketches	Initial sketches	Final sketches
Bus stop (5 students)	Swing(x3)	<i>Lego</i>	Smoke	<i>Sand dune</i>	Leaf (x3)	-	-	<i>Moving with wind (x2)</i>	Curtain	<i>Voting poll</i>
	Umbrella		Snowflakes		Shell				Knitting	
	Tent		Falling raindrops		Flower				Mobile	
	Zeppelin		Changing light		Bird					
			Moving grass		Butterfly					
		Cloud		Tree						
Packaging (5 students)	Pills	<i>Football</i>	Sponge	-	Fly	-	Diving in water	<i>Getting thin</i>	-	-
	Balloon (vehicle)	<i>Balloon</i>	Bubbles		Butterfly		Being thrown from a cannonball			
	Pillow	<i>Bowl</i>			Insect					
	Balloon	<i>Steel structure</i>			Tree					
	Bodum tea cup				Leaf					
MP3 Player (4 students)	-	<i>Post-it</i>	-	<i>Ice cube</i>	Insect	-	-	<i>Adding/removing sticks</i>	Windows volume icon	<i>Zen rocks</i>
					Feather					
				Stingray						
ATM (2 students)	-	<i>Paper</i>	-	<i>Falling leaves</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	11	7	11	3	13	-	2	4	4	2
	18		14		13		6		6	

While looking for product metaphor ideas, students firstly made a comprehensive investigation to find the most appropriate source domain. This investigation included not only very typical representatives of lightness like leaf, feather, bubble, etc., but also more uncommon interpretations like teacup and pills. When the sketches are carefully examined, we observed that the sources used in this phase could be categorized as nature-related entities, man-made objects, living organisms, actions, and other cultural phenomena. These categories indicate which areas designers consider when searching for sources. Nature-related entities involve geographic formations and natural events, man-made objects refer to everyday objects and vehicles, living things suggest humans, animals and plants, actions involve movements including embodied ones, and lastly, cultural phenomena refer to culturally learned concepts or things that cannot be considered as everyday objects.

As can be seen in Table 1, students considered various potential sources from these categories. They then evaluated the applicability of these sources for using in product metaphors and made their selections. When the reasons behind the selection of specific sources are carefully analyzed through interviews and sketches, two complementary aspects appear:

(1) Conveying the intended meaning saliently:

Students looked for sources that are in line with the meaning they intend to convey. If they wanted to convey lightness in terms of 'lightweight' for instance, they looked for sources that have 'being light in weight' as a salient property. Therefore, even though there were some potential sources that somehow have this property like falling raindrops, stingray fish and teacup, these were not selected in the final sketches since they were not good representatives of lightness and thus, they would not convey the lightweight meaning strongly. Rather, they chose comparatively more relevant sources to be able to communicate the intended meaning more effectively.

(2) Matching with the attributes of target domain (allowing for appropriate mappings):

This aspect is closely linked with the succeeding phase of mapping. Since designers are the ones who make the mapping in product metaphors, they carefully consider if the attributes of the potential source can match properly with those of the target domain. The following situation clearly explains this aspect: Leaf is a stereotypical exemplar of lightness, and therefore, it was considered as a potential source by the students who are designing chips packaging, ATM and bus stop (see Table 1). But after taking into consideration their target product only one student proceeded to work with this source because he was able to make a sound connection between leaves and money in terms of their form and movement. Therefore, it can be stated that during the design process students kept in mind how they would do the mapping and decided on the final source according to its potential for proper mapping.

3.2.3. Making the mapping from the source to the target domain

While selecting the source, students searched for proper matching attributes between source and target that can lead to apt and pleasurable metaphors. When we analyzed which attributes of the source are mapped to target, we identified three aspects. To elaborate on these, we may have a look at Figure 3. In Figure 3a, a MP3 player with the physical properties of a post-it can be seen. Post-it was chosen because it is lightweight, and its *sensorial properties* like form, color, weight and dimensions are mapped onto the MP3 player. In Figure 3b, a chips packaging that 'loses weight' every time one gets a chips out of it can be seen. In this example, the *movement* of getting smaller was mapped onto the package. Lastly, in Figure 3c, there is a bus stop metaphor that Lego was selected as a source domain. The people waiting for a bus *interact* with the pieces that compose the bus stop, as they would play with actual Lego's. Thus, designers either shape the target product like the source, make the product move/behave like the source or guide the user to interact with the product in a similar way of interacting with the source. In brief, we can state that after deciding on the source domain, its sensorial properties, movements and/or interaction patterns are mapped to the matching attributes of the target product. It should again be noted that designers also anticipate the matching of these aspects between target and source while they decide on the source. Therefore, selecting the source domain and making the mapping are closely linked phases, in which designers plan the latter one while they go through the former phase.

Figure 3. Mappings of sensorial properties (a), movement (b) and interaction (c).

Another aspect that was observed is that when the selected source domains properly match with the target domain, a rich usage scenario follows. The entire context of the source domain can be used to explain and enhance the product-user interaction. To illustrate, a student used 'leaf' as a potential source for chips packaging. This association led him to shape the package as leaf (sensorial property mapping from 'leaf' to 'package'), and then he hung the packages to the sales-point stand as if they were the leaves on a tree (sensorial property mapping from 'tree' to 'stand'). In his scenario, when users wanted to buy chips, they shook the stand like they would do to a real tree (interaction pattern mapping from 'tree' to 'stand'). Then, the packages fall from the tree in a fluttering action like leaves (movement mapping from 'leaf' to 'package'). This chosen source brings in many additional elements to the usage scenario since it has a rich context matching aptly with the context of the target domain.

Mapping making not only includes deciding on which attributes to match but also selecting 'how' to match these attributes. With the analysis of the sketches we identified different strategies. First of all, some students wanted to make the association between source and target explicitly perceivable in order to make the metaphor identifiable and understandable, while some of them preferred their association to be subtle and less perceivable. In Figure 4a, the student created an association between fluttering leaves and money, and he explicitly used that movement in the money receiving process from an ATM. The metaphor in Figure 4b involves an implicit mapping from an ice cube to MP3 player, which may not be identifiable by the users very easily because of the differences in material, size and weight. Another difference in terms of mapping is in the extent of literal or abstracted mapping. Some students took the attributes of source domain and transferred them to the attributes of target without making any changes. For instance, in Figure 5a we can see a mapping from balloon to chips packaging, and the way a person holds and carries balloons are directly applied to package without further manipulation. On the other hand, in Figure 5b the student chose sand dune as a source for her bus stop metaphor since dunes change their forms according to the wind. With her organic and free-flowing bus stop, she abstracted a sand dune for her final metaphor design.

Figure 4. Explicit (a) and implicit (b) mappings

Figure 5. Literal (c) and abstracted (d) mappings

4. Discussion

First of all, we would like to start by commenting on the design process in general. As has been noted, in this workshop we followed a process that starts with meaning definition, continues with source selection and ends with mapping making from source to target. The workshop outcomes indicate that this kind of an approach actually works given that the students were able to create many product metaphor ideas. However, our informal conversations with students after the workshop pointed out some concerns regarding the design process. During the workshop we deliberately did not provide any guidance or detailed information alongside the design brief. Some students specifically emphasized that they liked the openness of the brief and the freedom during the metaphor generation process seeing that there were no limitations and demands. On the contrary, some others complained about this freedom indicating that they felt lost sometimes. They expressed that a more extensive brief providing an explicit and detailed guidance on the process would be more helpful. As a matter of fact, not providing guidance was our conscious choice that we wanted to get some insights about how they deal with metaphor generation and what kind of a process they follow. Our first insights indicate that the assertions of interactive property attribution model can be considered valid also for product metaphors. To briefly remind, this theory holds that when people produce a metaphor they look for a good representative of the meaning they want to attribute to target. The source that best exemplifies this meaning does not depend on the target; however, the target plays a role in providing relevant dimensions for attribution [11]. Correspondingly, students had a similar process during their design exercise. As noted before, students first looked for a representative source to convey lightness, evaluated them with regard to the target product and questioned if it was reasonable to create a connection between two. That's why we cannot see any feathers and butterflies in the final sketches. We mentioned before that students kept in mind how they would do the mapping and decided on the final source according to its potential for proper mapping. Therefore, it can be stated that the assertion of source and target playing different roles in metaphor generation is also valid for product metaphors.

Regarding the phases of this process, first of all we can state that the meaning intended to be conveyed through metaphor usage should be clear for designers to able to start metaphor generation process. In an actual design process, designers would have a lucid idea about this meaning and which dimensions they would want to emphasize since they know what they want to communicate. However in our workshop, students were asked to generate metaphors for a pre-identified meaning, which triggered the need to clarify it. We observed that lightness was considered to be rather ambiguous concept; therefore students described it according to their perceptions and interpretations. After clarifying the meaning, they explored various areas in order to find an

appropriate source for the metaphor. These areas included nature-related entities, biology, actions, man-made products or other cultural phenomena; and they considered many representatives of the intended meaning from these areas. Unquestionably, all the source domains considered in this stage are concrete and real world entities. This is in correspondence with previously mentioned arguments of Katz [6] who claims people prefer concrete sources over abstract ones. This situation is quite logical since metaphors make abstract ideas concrete. However, it should be noted that, in language using an abstract source domain is possible like in the example of 'flying is freedom'. Yet, the reason for using concrete sources in product metaphors is different. Products are tangible entities by their very nature, and therefore, every idea we aim to apply to them should be transformed into a tangible and perceivable form. This means that source domains cannot be abstract in product metaphors. The meaning designers want to convey can be abstract, but then they have to find a concrete carrier of that meaning in order to apply this meaning to the target product.

After considering a variety of concrete candidate sources, students then selected one of them according to two complementary aspects. If a source conveys the intended meaning properly and allows for good mappings, it is selected for the final design. As a matter of fact, the selection of a particular source domain is a combination of these aspects. As the designers aim to create metaphors that convey the intended meaning in an appropriate and aesthetic way, both of these aspects are the reasons of source selection. If the source they select does not convey the intended meaning in an understandable way it is not successful in achieving the aims of metaphor usage, and if it does not properly match with the target domain it is not understandable and/or pleasurable as a metaphor. For all these reasons, these two aspects are complementary and contribute to the selection of a source domain together. Source selection is followed by the mapping process. As noted before, these two stages are intertwined. While deciding on the source, designers have to take into account the mapping process by considering the target product.

To conclude we can state that metaphor generation requires a considerable amount of decision-making. Designers have to decide on the meaning they will convey, the source that can convey this meaning, which attributes of this source they will map and how they will do the mapping. With good and creative decisions with respect to these aspects, they can create understandable and pleasurable metaphors, and therefore provide rich user experiences. The present study is one of the first attempts to include metaphors as a research subject in product design. If we develop our knowledge in metaphor generation process, we can provide the product experience domain the necessary theoretical knowledge concerning the role, functions, and design procedure of product metaphors, as well as design practice the necessary insights and inspiration for creating successful metaphors.

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